

1 Statistical Analysis Plan

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112 **1 Abbreviations and Definitions**

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Abbreviation	Definition
HEPA	High-efficiency particulate air
ITT	Intention-to-treat
CADR	Clean air delivery rate
MNAR	Missing not at random
NA	<i>Not applicable</i>
IRR	<i>Incidence rate ratio</i>
MCAR	<i>Missing completely at random</i>
MAR	<i>Missing at random</i>
IPW	<i>Inverse probability weighted</i>
MI	<i>Multiple imputation</i>
HVACs	<i>Heating, ventilation and air condition systems</i>
OR	<i>Marginal odds ratio</i>
MD	<i>Population-averaged mean difference</i>
PPM	<i>Parts per million</i>
GEE	<i>Generalizing estimating equations</i>
ICC	<i>Intraclass cluster correlation</i>
FDA	<i>US Food and drug administration</i>
QLC	<i>Quasi-likelihood criterion</i>
SES	<i>Socioeconomic status</i>

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138 **2 Introduction**

139 **2.1 Preface**

140 Respiratory infections like influenza and SARS-CoV-2 pose significant global health risks due to their
141 potential high transmissibility and severity. SARS-CoV-2 has caused over 7 million deaths worldwide,
142 and the Lancet Commission estimates a >20% chance of another respiratory virus pandemic within a
143 decade. Schools are high-risk settings for transmission, with outbreaks causing substantial disruptions
144 for teachers, students, and parents. While school closures reduce transmission, they can also lead to
145 learning loss and societal burdens. Air purifiers with HEPA filters may offer a non-disruptive mitigation
146 strategy, but at the time of writing only one randomized trial has been conducted, with unpublished
147 results, highlighting the need for further research.

148
149 This statistical analysis plan describes the analysis for a cluster-randomized, parallel, two-arm, group
150 sequential superiority trial that aims to estimate the effect of air purifiers compared to sham air
151 purifiers on absenteeism among primary school children in Norway (primary research question);
152 secondary research questions are listed below.

153 **2.2 Research Questions**

154 The study's research questions and their corresponding estimands are summarized in Table 1; the
155 estimands are presented in a simplified form (see section 5 for full details).

156
157 Table 1 — Summary of study research questions and associated estimands

Primary research question	Estimand (simplified)
Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA filters in classrooms reduce student absenteeism?	Incidence rate ratio comparing rate of student absence between intervention and control arms.
Secondary research questions	
Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA filters in classrooms reduce teacher absenteeism due to respiratory infections?	Incidence rate ratio comparing rate of self-reported teacher absence due to illness between intervention and control arms.
Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA filters in classrooms reduce incidence of respiratory infection among teachers?	Incidence rate ratio comparing rate of self-reported events of respiratory infections among teachers between intervention and control arms.
Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA filters in classroom reduce numbers of teachers reporting at least one respiratory infection during a 12-week period?	Odds ratio comparing the 12-week odds of teachers reporting at least one respiratory infection between intervention and control arms.
Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA filters improve teachers' perceptions of air quality in classrooms?	Mean difference in teachers' MM40 standard questionnaire scores for perceived air quality between intervention and control arms, assessed after 12 weeks (end of the study).
What is the rate of adverse events in schools with air purifiers with HEPA filters, and is this rate different in school with sham air purifiers?	Incidence rates of adverse events and an incidence rate ratio comparing these rates between intervention and control arms.

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163 The treatment “installing and operating” means that we will install air purifiers and shams, and
164 “operate” them by instructing a contact person at each school (e.g., a school janitor) to ensure that
165 they are running as intended, according to a typical maintenance schedule. The word “operating” here
166 does not mean that the air purifiers and shams will be operational (running) 100% of the time, or that
167 we will account for non-operational (out-of-order) status as an intercurrent event. Section “Strategy
168 for handling intercurrent events” in section 5 addresses this issue in more detail. The estimands we
169 define are therefore all intention-to-treat (ITT) rather than per-protocol estimands (or similar).

170 **3 Methods**

171 **3.1 General Study Design and Plan**

172

Populations	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Primary school children in grades 5–7 inclusive (typically aged 10-13 years).2. School teachers (of children in grades 5–7 inclusive).
Intervention	Install and operate two air purifiers per intervention school classroom. The air purifiers will operate at a performance equivalent to 3.0 air changes per hour with two air purifiers installed in each classroom, providing a combined capacity to a Clean Air Delivery Rate (CADR) of at least 486 m ³ /hour.
Control	Install and operate two modified air purifiers per control school classroom, which will be referred to as “sham” air purifiers throughout this document for brevity. These air purifiers will operate at a performance equivalent to 0.3 air changes per hour, providing a combined CADR of at least 48 m ³ /hour.
Primary outcome Design	Number of full student days of absence from school. Cluster-randomized, parallel, two-arm, group sequential superiority trial with one interim analysis (binding for efficacy, nonbinding for futility). Data for the first look will be collected during winter season 2025/2026. If the trial continues to a second look, data will be collected during winter season 2026/2027.
Blinding	School staff, participating teachers, and students will be blinded to treatment allocation via the use of sham air purifiers in the control group. The statistician will be blinded and will blind the research group when presenting results.
Treatment allocation	Schools (clusters) will be randomized 1:1 to intervention or control using covariate-constrained randomization to ensure approximately identical distributions of key baseline variables.

173

174

175
176 Figure 1 Illustrates the trial timeline and process

177 **3.2 General Study Populations and Inclusion-Exclusion Criteria**

178 There are two general study populations. The first population is primary school children in Norway.
179 Primary schools meeting the following criteria will be eligible:

- 180
- 181 1. Schools with more than 10 students in either 5th, 6th, or 7th grade (typically aged 10-13 years).
 - 182 2. Schools with at least one classroom of sufficient dimensions to accommodate the installation of
 - 183 two air purifiers.
 - 184 3. The school principal accepts the installation of air purifiers in at least one classroom in the 5th, 6th,
 - 185 or 7th grade that meets the first two inclusion criteria.

186
187 The second population is teachers at primary school children in Norway. Teachers meeting the
188 following criteria will be eligible:

- 189
- 190 1. Be the main class teacher of one or more of the classrooms included in the study.
 - 191 2. Provide informed consent.

192 **3.3 Treatment Allocation**

193 The unit of randomization is school. Treatments will be allocated 1:1 to intervention and control
194 schools using covariate-constrained randomization after obtaining consent from school principals. We
195 will specify the random number generator seed to be the arbitrary integer 1234 (see below), ensuring
196 that we cannot manipulate the randomization and that it is reproducible.

197
198 To ensure approximately identical distributions of baseline variables that we assume are prognostic,
199 we will use covariate-constrained randomization using the baseline covariates: **school_logco2**
200 (mean log CO₂ concentration), **school_logabsrate** (log mean student absence rate),
201 **ventilation** (schools' existing mixing vs. displacement ventilation), **income** (median household
202 income after tax in the School district ["delområde"]), which we use as an index of socioeconomic
203 status (SES), and **students_7thgrade** (number of students in 7th grade).

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208 CO₂ concentration and student absence will be measured weekly at the level of classroom in the pre-
 209 randomization phase of the trial. However, randomization will be performed at the level of school, so
 210 it is necessary to aggregate the covariates at the school level. We will aggregate baseline log CO₂
 211 concentration measurements by computing the variable `school_logco2` as:

212

$$213 \quad \text{school_logco2} = \frac{1}{N} \sum c_{i,j,k}$$

214

215 where $c_{i,j,k}$ is the log CO₂ concentration in school i , class j , at week k , and the sum is implicitly over N
 216 classrooms and weeks. We will compute the variable `school_logabsrate` as:

217

$$218 \quad \text{school_logabsrate} = \log \sum \frac{1}{E_{i,j}} a_{i,j,k}$$

219

220 where $a_{i,j,k}$ is the number of student-days of absences in school i , classroom j , at week k , $E_{i,j}$ is the
 221 total exposure in school i and classroom j .

222

223 We selected median household income after tax as our socioeconomic status (SES) index following
 224 consultation with Statistics Norway (Statistisk sentralbyrå; SSB). SSB publishes these data at the district
 225 level (delområde), which represents subdivisions of municipalities (kommuner) comprising aggregated
 226 basic statistical areas (grunnkretser). Districts are defined to ensure statistical stability and temporal
 227 comparability. We will geocode participating schools to their respective districts and assign each school
 228 the most recently available median household income for its district as the school-level SES measure.

229

230 We will randomize using the `cvcrand` Stata add-on command for covariate-constrained
 231 randomization of clusters in a two-arm parallel cluster randomized trial [1]. For the first look, we will
 232 randomize 32 schools (see section 7), giving $\binom{32}{32/2} \approx 600$ million possible randomizations. We will
 233 measure covariate balance using the ℓ_2 balance metric (`cvcrand`'s default) and randomly select from
 234 among the most balanced 1% ≈ 6 million randomizations, using syntax like

235

```
236 cvcrand school_logco2 school_logabsrate ventilation income students_7thgrade, ///
237 seed(1234) ntotal_cluster(32) ntrt_cluster(16) clustername(school) ///
238 categorical(ventilation) cutoff(0.01)
```

239

240 If the trial proceeds to the second look, we will randomize an additional 30 schools (see section 7),
 241 which equates to an additional $\binom{30}{30/2} \approx 155$ million possible randomizations. We will perform
 242 randomization in the same way as for the first look, randomly selecting from among the most balanced
 243 1% ≈ 1.6 million randomizations, using syntax like

244

```
245 cvcrand school_logco2 school_logabsrate ventilation income students_7thgrade, ///
246 seed(1234) ntotal_cluster(30) ntrt_cluster(15) clustername(school) ///
247 categorical(ventilation) cutoff(0.01)
```

248

249 3.4 Blinding/Masking

250 School staff, participating teachers, students and researchers responsible for installing the air purifiers
 251 will be blinded to treatment allocation using sham air purifiers in the control group.

252

253 The trial uses a group sequential design with one interim analysis (binding for efficacy, nonbinding for
254 futility). If the analysis result for the primary estimand crosses the prespecified boundary for efficacy,
255 the trial must be stopped early. If not, the trial may continue or stop at the discretion of the research
256 team. Table 2 presents the stopping boundary z-values that define efficacy and futility.

257
258 At the interim analysis, a member of the research group will blind the statistician by arbitrarily labelling
259 the trial arms “A” and “B”. At this stage, at least that member of the research will not be blinded, but
260 the statistician will be. The statistician will perform the interim analysis for the primary outcome. The
261 statistician will then apply a blind to the results, arbitrarily labelling the trial arms “C” and “D” so that
262 all members of the research group will be blinded to treatment allocation. To minimize the risk that
263 the research group can guess the direction of any treatment effect based on numbers of events and
264 exposures, the statistician will exclude this information from their report.

265
266 While blinded, the research group will discuss and agree how the result of the interim analysis of the
267 primary outcome can be interpreted under the two possible treatment allocations. We will publish a
268 short document on Zenodo describing these interpretations.

269
270 In the event of **futility at the interim analysis**, the decision to stop or continue the trial will be made
271 blinded. If we decide to continue the trial, we will not unblind.

272
273 We will stop the trial in the event of **efficacy at the interim analysis**. Once the trial is stopped (either
274 at the interim or second analysis), the statistician will analyze all outcomes while blinded and will blind
275 the research group to the results as described above. The research group will discuss and agree how
276 the results of the analyses of all outcomes can be interpreted under the two possible treatment
277 allocations. We will publish a short document on Zenodo describing these interpretations. We will then
278 unblind and report the trial using the published interpretations.

279 **3.5 Safety and acceptability**

280 We will monitor safety and acceptability throughout the trial and will stop the trial if we have good
281 reason to believe that air purifiers are unsafe or unacceptably impact student education. We will ask
282 schools to report the number of adverse events associated with the air purifiers and shams.
283 Specifically, we will ask the schools to report any incidents that significantly disrupt lessons or cause
284 accidents or injuries during the trial. We will assess safety each month using the numbers of reported
285 adverse events. If a school does not report any adverse events in a given month, then the number of
286 reported adverse events is zero (we will not consider unreported adverse events).

287
288 Because we expect air purifiers and shams to be indistinguishable, we do not anticipate being able to
289 detect a statistical difference in the rates of adverse events between the trial arms. While we will
290 estimate an incidence rate ratio for this outcome, any decision to stop the trial will be made on the
291 basis of the total number of adverse events, aggregated across trial arms.

292 **4 Variables**

293 This section provides an overview of the variables that will be measured or derived for randomization,
294 statistical analysis, and reporting. Additional variables may be used to support other aspects of the
295 trial. The variables are summarized in Table 2.

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Table 2. Summary of variables

Variable	Measurement Level ¹	Definition	Timing
----------	--------------------------------	------------	--------

Trial-level variables

treat	School	Treatment assignment (see section 3.4)	NA
week	NA	Week number.	Weekly
phase	NA	Factor variable with levels: pre1 , post1 , pre2 , post2 (see text).	Weekly
school	School	School ID (unique across the trial).	NA
classroom	Classroom < School	Classroom ID (unique across the trial).	NA
teacher	Teacher < School	Teacher ID (unique across the trial).	NA
Baseline covariates (measured before randomization)			
logco2	Week < Classroom < School	Log CO ₂ concentration in a classroom.	Weekly
school_logco2	School	Log CO ₂ concentration in a school (averaged over week and classroom).	@Baseline
student_absence	Week < Classroom < School	Number of student-days of absence in a classroom.	Weekly
school_logabsrate	School	Log mean rate of student absences.	@Baseline
ventilation	School	Factor variable with levels: mixing and displacementnatural	@Baseline
income	School	Median household income after tax	@Baseline
students_7thgrade	School	Number of students in 7th grade	@Baseline
Outcome and exposure variables (measured after randomization)			
student_absence	Week < Classroom < School	Primary outcome. Number of student-days of absence in a classroom	Weekly
student_exposure	Week < Classroom < School	Number of student-days of exposure in a classroom	Weekly
teacher_absence	Week < Teacher < School	Number of teacher-days of work absence	Weekly
teacher_exposure	Week < Teacher < School	Number of teacher-days of exposure	
teacher_events	Week < Teacher < School	Number of incidence of respiratory symptoms consistent with respiratory infections among teachers	Weekly
teacher_infection	Teacher < School	Dichotomous variable indicating whether teachers report at least one event of symptoms consistent with respiratory infection	@3 months
teacher_mm040	Teacher < School	Score on the MM040 questionnaire, measured at the level of teacher, at the end of the 3-month period	@3 months
adverse_events	School	Number of times air purifiers were reported to significantly disrupt lessons or cause accidents or injuries	Monthly
Auxiliary variables			
L.student_absence	Week < Classroom < School	Number of student-days of absence in a classroom, lagged by one week	Weekly
L.teacher_absence	Week < Classroom < School	Number of teacher-days of work absence, lagged by one week	Weekly
urban_rural	School	Factor variable with levels urban & rural	Baseline
school_size	School	Number of students in the school	Baseline
class_size	Classroom < School	Number of students enrolled in the classroom	Baseline
L.logco2	Classroom < School	logco2 , lagged by one week	Weekly

1. Clustering of X in Y is indicated as X < Y.

299 The variable **week** is a factor variable that codes for week number. We will code the weeks as
300 1, 2, 3, ..., giving each week a unique number across the trial phases.
301

302 The variable **phase** is a factor variable that codes for trial phase with levels:

- 303 1. **pre1** pre-randomization phase for the first look.
- 304 2. **post1** post-randomization phase for the first look.
- 305 3. **pre2** pre-randomization phase for the second look.
- 306 4. **post2** post-randomization phase for the second look.

307 This variable may be derived from the **week** variable provided the week number is known for the first
308 week of each phase.

309

310 The variables **school**, **classroom**, and **teacher** are factor variables that identify each school,
311 classroom, and teacher, respectively. We will not reuse school, classroom, or teacher identifiers across
312 trial phases, schools, or classes (i.e., each will be uniquely identified across the entire trial). In principle
313 a classroom could have more than one teacher, with teachers clustered within classroom within
314 school. It is also possible that teachers teach in more than one classroom within a school (or perhaps
315 across schools). In practice we anticipate these scenarios will be uncommon, that there will be one
316 teacher per classroom, and it will be sufficient to model the clustering of teachers as teacher within
317 school.

318

319 The auxiliary variables will be used to estimate inverse probability weights if outcome data are missing
320 (see section 5.1). We hypothesize there could be a difference in the probability that outcome data will
321 be reported (nonmissing) with respect to:

- 322 • Student and teacher absences (the lagged variables `L.student_absence` and
323 `L.teacher_absence`) from the previous week. For example, perhaps staff would be reluctant
324 to report absences in a given week if absences were also high in the previous week.
- 325 • The location (`urban_rural`) and size (defined as number of students) of schools and
326 classrooms (`school_size` and `class_size`). For example, perhaps staff in urban or larger
327 schools would be busier than those in rural or smaller schools and would be less likely to
328 report absences due to time pressures.

329

330 We anticipate that a teacher may be less likely to report outcomes if they are unwell, which could lead
331 to a missing not at random (MNAR) scenario for some outcomes (e.g., MM 040 score). Section 5.1
332 described how we will address the MNAR scenario.

333 5 Estimands

334 All estimands compare the intervention (installing and operating two air purifiers per classroom) to
335 the control (installing and operating two *sham* air purifiers per classroom). A summary of the data
336 measures and estimands is shown in Table 3.

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Table 3. Summary of estimands and data measures.

Estimand	Outcome type	Numerator	Exposure	Data source	Timepoint	Measurement	Summary
----------	--------------	-----------	----------	-------------	-----------	-------------	---------

						level	measure
Primary estimand							
Student absence	Count	Number of full student-days of absence	Estimated number of student-days of exposure	Schools' absence registration system	Weekly	Class level	IRR
Secondary estimands							
Teachers self-reported sick leave	Count	Number of full teacher-days of absence due to respiratory infection	Estimated number of teacher-days of exposure	Weekly questionnaire	Weekly	Teacher level	IRR
Incidence of self-reported respiratory infection among teachers	Count	Number of teacher-incidents of respiratory infection	Estimated number of teacher-days of exposure	Weekly questionnaire	Weekly	Teacher level	IRR
Number of teachers reporting respiratory infections	Count	Number of teachers reporting respiratory infections	Number of teachers	Weekly questionnaire	Weekly	Teacher level	OR
Teachers perceived air-quality	Continuous	Rating of classroom air quality	Number of consenting teachers	MM40 questionnaire at the end of intervention	End of intervention period	Teacher level	MD
Adverse events	Count	Reported number of adverse events	Total classroom days over study period	Monthly questionnaire	Monthly	School	IRR

N/A = not applicable, IRR = Incidence Rate Ratio

348 5.1 Primary estimand — Student-days of absence rate ratio

349 Research question

350 The primary estimand addresses the question “Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA
351 filters in classrooms reduce student absenteeism?”.

352 Population

353 Primary school children in Norway.

354 Outcome variable

355 The outcome for the primary estimand (i.e., the primary outcome) is **student_absence**, the
356 number of student days of school absence, measured each week at the level of class (note that class is
357 clustered within school). The variable is therefore a count.

358

359 We will define a student day of absence as a day for which a student is absent for the entire day. We
360 will not distinguish between the specific students who are absent (i.e., two days of absence will be
361 counted for one student who is absent on two days, and for two students absent for one day each).

362 **Exposure variable**

363 We will estimate treatment effect using an incidence rate ratio (IRR) at the level of classroom
364 (see below), so it is necessary to assess exposure. Enrollment data for each classroom will be obtained
365 as baseline, defined as the number of children expected to attend each classroom. We will collect data
366 on the number of children present in each classroom for each school day during outcome collection.
367 Based on these data, **student_exposure** will be calculated in units of student-days throughout
368 the trial period.

369
370 While new students may join or leave a class (e.g., due to relocation), we anticipate that this will be
371 sufficiently rare that it is unlikely to meaningfully change or improve the calculation of exposure, so
372 we will not attempt to account for it. For example, one student in a classroom of 23 students who
373 leaves half-way through the trial would only change the computed exposure for that class by about
374 2%, which is less than 0.1% of the total exposure across the trial as a whole at the first look.

375 **Treatment effect measure**

376 We will measure treatment effect for the primary estimand using a population-averaged IRR that
377 compares rates of student-days of absences in intervention and control schools. We will estimate the
378 IRR as described in section 10.1.

379
380 Treatment effect will be estimated following the ITT principle: all classrooms from all randomized
381 schools will be included and analyzed in the arms to which they were randomized.

382 **Strategy for handling missing data**

383 If, despite repeated requests, a school does not make any outcome data available to us, we will assume
384 the school has withdrawn consent and will exclude the school from analysis. We will however report
385 if any schools are excluded for this reason.

386
387 We anticipate that it will not be possible to distinguish between there being no absences for a given
388 week and absence data being missing for a given week. If absence data are not recorded for a
389 classroom for a given week, we will assume that the data are correctly not reported (i.e., we will impute
390 that there were no absences). However, if no absences are reported for a given classroom for two
391 consecutive weeks, we will contact the school to verify the accuracy of the recorded data, because this
392 scenario is unlikely. If the school does not confirm that the absence data are correct or provide absence
393 data, we will treat the absence data as missing. We will not implement additional follow-up measures,
394 such as weekly SMS reminders.

395
396 We will use the missing indicator method if data are missing for any of the covariates [2].

397
398 If outcome data are missing for $\leq 5\%$ of observations (i.e., rows where each row corresponds to a
399 particular school, classroom, and week), then we will proceed under the assumption that the data can
400 be treated as missing completely at random (MCAR) [3].

401
402 If outcome data are missing for $> 5\%$ of observations, we will formally assess the missingness
403 mechanism using the following two-step procedure:

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 1. **Test for Missing Completely at Random (MCAR):** We will use Little's overall χ^2 test to evaluate
410 the null hypothesis that the outcomes are missing completely at random (MCAR).

- 411 a. **If the null hypothesis is not rejected ($p \geq 0.05$):** We will proceed under the working
412 assumption that the data are MCAR and conduct a complete case analysis. However,
413 we acknowledge that this test has limited power and will also perform a MNAR
414 sensitivity analysis using Manski-like bounds as described below.
- 415 b. **If the null hypothesis is rejected ($p < 0.05$):** We will proceed to step 2 to explore
416 whether missingness is conditionally independent of the outcome given observed
417 covariates (i.e., MAR).
- 418 2. **Test for covariate-dependent missingness (CDM):** We will fit a logistic regression model where
419 the dependent variable is an indicator of missingness in the outcome. The independent
420 variables will include the covariates used in the constrained randomization and prespecified
421 auxiliary variables. We will then use a Wald test of the joint null hypothesis that none of these
422 covariates are associated with missingness.
- 423 a. **If the null hypothesis is not rejected ($p \geq 0.05$):** We will proceed under the assumption
424 that the data are missing at random (MAR). In this case, we will use an inverse
425 probability weighting (IPW) approach for analysis, as described below.
- 426 b. **If the null hypothesis is rejected ($p < 0.05$):** We will proceed under the assumption
427 that the data may be missing not at random (MNAR) and will estimate Manski-like
428 bounds for the primary estimand as described below.

429
430 Under the MCAR assumption, we will perform a complete case analysis.

431

432 Under the MAR assumption, we will perform an inverse probability weighted (IPW) analysis using a
433 similar approach to that described by Seaman and White [4]. We will use cross-validated elastic net
434 logistic regression to model the probability that outcome data are observed, accounting for the cluster-
435 randomized design. Predictor variables will be selected from the covariates used in the constrained
436 randomization and from auxiliary variables. We will then use the predicted probabilities in the IPW
437 analysis. We chose IPW over multiple imputation (MI) to make estimation computationally tractable.
438 Section 10 describes how we will use simulation for conditional maximum likelihood estimation; the
439 combination of MI and simulation will be excessively computationally expensive.

440

441 Under the MNAR assumption, will estimate Manski-like bounds for the primary estimand to provide
442 an interval estimate with sharp bounds on treatment effect under conditions in which missing
443 outcomes maximally favor or disfavor the intervention [5]. One bound can be computed by imputing
444 that all students in **control** classrooms with missing outcome data were **absent** for the entire week,
445 and that all students in **intervention** classrooms with missing outcome data were **present** for the entire
446 week; the other bound can be computed by imputing the opposite. These estimates will be reported
447 as intervals (rather than points) and confidence intervals.

448

449 Under the MNAR scenario, we will also estimate “soft” bounds on the treatment effect by specifying
450 two less extreme but still plausible missing data scenarios. In the first scenario, we will impute that
451 50% of students in control classrooms with missing outcome data for a given week were absent for the
452 entire week, while 50% of students in intervention classrooms with missing data were present for the
453 entire week. In the second scenario, we will reverse these assumptions. These scenarios are designed
454 to reflect directional assumptions that favor or disfavor the intervention, but with more tempered
455 imputations than the sharp bounds. The resulting treatment effect estimate will be reported as an
456 interval and a confidence interval.

457

458 Vinterferie ("winter holiday") is a one-week school closure that occurs annually in February or March.
459 Outcomes are not defined when schools are closed (e.g., it is not possible for a student to be absent
460 from a school that is not in session). This represents a structural feature of the follow-up period rather
461 than missing data. The vinterferie week will be excluded from outcome measurement and analysis.

462 **Strategy for handling intercurrent events**

463 We have assessed the following possible intercurrent events and determined that they are inherent to
464 the intervention as we envision it would likely be implemented outside a trial. The events are therefore
465 a natural part of treatment, and we will not account for them in analysis.

- 466
- 467 • Changes or adjustments to classrooms' existing ventilation systems (e.g., HVAC systems).
 - 468 • Additional air quality interventions (e.g., use of existing or new air purifiers, opening doors or
469 windows, changes in cleaning protocols that might affect air quality).
 - 470 • Changes in student or teacher attendance patterns (e.g., absences not due to illness, school trips,
471 students joining or leaving a class due to relocation, replacement or substitution of teachers).
 - 472 • Behavioral changes due to the installation of a new device in the classroom (as distinct from
473 knowing whether the device is a functional air purifier or a sham).
 - 474 • External events affecting air quality or the probability of respiratory infection (e.g., industrial
475 emissions, localized outbreaks).
 - 476 • Malfunction or misuse of the air purifiers or shams.
 - 477 • Changes in school, local, or national policies affecting the children, school staff, or children's
478 parents or guardians (e.g., masking and hand hygiene requirements, vaccination campaigns).
 - 479 • Cross-contamination between schools randomized to a different treatment (e.g., visiting a school
480 randomized to the other treatment; social events with children, teachers, or parents or guardians
481 of those randomized to the other treatment).
 - 482 • Changes in outdoor routines (e.g., spending more or less time outdoors before school, during
483 breaks, or after school).
- 484

485 The week in which vinterferie is observed varies across Norway. Schools in the sampling frame (the
486 Østlandet region) observe vinterferie in one of two different weeks. In principle, vinterferie could be
487 considered an intercurrent event, because outcomes measured after vinterferie may have a different
488 interpretation from those measured before (e.g., absences following vinterferie may reflect infections
489 acquired outside the school setting). However, vinterferie is a structural feature of the school calendar,
490 rather than an unplanned post-randomization event. The primary estimand is therefore defined to
491 reflect the effect of the intervention under usual school operating conditions over the study period,
492 including scheduled holidays. Consequently, vinterferie will not be treated as an intercurrent event.
493 Instead, its timing will be accounted for in the analysis to ensure appropriate comparison of outcomes
494 across schools with different holiday weeks.

495

496 **5.2 Secondary estimand — Teacher-days of absence due to respiratory infection**
497 **rate ratio**

498 **Research question**

499 This secondary estimand addresses the question “Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA
500 filters in classrooms reduce teacher absenteeism due to respiratory infections?”.

501 **Population**

502 Primary school teachers in Norway.
503

504 **Outcome variable**

505 The outcome for this estimand is **teacher_absence**, the number of days of work absence due to
506 respiratory infection, measured each week at the level of teacher (note that teacher is clustered within
507 school). The variable is therefore a count.
508

509 We will define a day of work absence as a day for which a teacher is absent for the entire day due to
510 respiratory infection. We will not distinguish between the specific days on which teachers are absent
511 (i.e., two days of absence will be counted for a teacher who is absent on two consecutive days, and for
512 a teacher who is absent on two nonconsecutive days).

513
514 Teachers will report absences retrospectively each week, responding to the question “How many days
515 were you absent from work last week due to respiratory illness?”. Teachers answering “Yes” to the
516 question “Did you experience symptoms of a cold, COVID-19 or the flu last week?” will be asked to
517 report the number of full days of absence for that week.

518 **Exposure variable**

519 Similarly to the **student_exposure** variable, we will use school timetables and teacher absence
520 data to compute the variable **teacher_exposure**, the number of teacher-days of exposure for
521 each teacher.

522 **Treatment effect measure**

523 We will measure treatment effect using a population-averaged incidence rate ratio (IRR) that compares
524 rates of teacher-days of absences in intervention and control schools. Section 5.1 describes how
525 estimation will be performed.

526
527 Treatment effect will be estimated following the intention-to-treat (ITT) principle: all teachers from all
528 randomized schools will be included and analyzed in the arms to which they were randomized.

529 **Strategy for handling missing data**

530 We will handle missing data using the approach described in section 5.1.

531 **Strategy for handling intercurrent events**

532 See section 5.1.

533 **5.3 Secondary estimand — Teacher-incidents of respiratory infection rate ratio**

534 **Research question**

535 This secondary estimand addresses the question “Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA
536 filters in classrooms reduce incident of respiratory infections among teachers?”.

537 **Population**

538 Primary school teachers in Norway.

539 **Outcome variable**

540 The outcome for this estimand is **teacher_events**, the number of incidents of symptoms
541 consistent with respiratory infection, measured each week at the level of teacher (note that teacher is
542 clustered within school). We define an incident as a period during which a teacher reports symptoms
543 for at least two consecutive days, preceded and followed by at least 7 symptom-free calendar days.
544 The variable is therefore a count.

545
546
547
548 A teacher will be defined to have experienced symptoms of a respiratory infection if they:

549
550 (1) Answering “yes” to the question “Did you experience symptoms of a cold, COVID-19 or the flu
551 last week?”.

- 552 (2) Reporting at least one of the following symptoms: nasal obstruction (plugged or congested),
553 nasal discharge (runny nose), sneezing or sore throat, in the last week;
- 554 (3) Scoring at least four points on the Jackson scale, based on symptom severity during the
555 preceding week (where symptoms are rated as absent (0), mild (1), moderate (2), or severe
556 (3));
- 557 (4) Reporting that they have experienced at least one of the reported symptoms for at least two
558 consecutive days in the last week.

559
560 This case definition mimics that suggested by the Wisconsin Upper Respiratory Symptom Survey
561 (WURSS) definition [6, 7]. The Jackson scale asks participants to rate the symptoms sneezing, nasal
562 discharge, nasal obstruction, sore throat, headache, malaise, chilliness, and cough from absent (0),
563 mild (1), moderate (2), or severe (3). The questions and other text will be presented to the teachers in
564 Norwegian.

565
566 Respiratory infection data will be self-reported by teachers and collected weekly throughout the trial
567 period. Teachers who answer “Yes” to the question “Did you experience symptoms of a cold, COVID-
568 19 or the flu last week?” will be asked to specify the symptoms they experienced (sore throat, cough,
569 runny nose, nasal congestion/stuffy nose, sneezing, headache, fever or general discomfort) and rate
570 their severity as mild, moderate, or severe. They will then report the number of days they experienced
571 these symptoms (ranging from 1 to 7 days), before answering “How many days were you absent from
572 work last week due to respiratory infection?”. A count of zero days will be assigned to teachers
573 answering “No” to the question above.

574
575 We will not distinguish between the specific days for which teachers experienced symptoms —
576 i.e., two days of symptoms will be counted as one event both for a teacher who reports symptoms on
577 two consecutive days, and for a teacher who reports symptoms on two nonconsecutive days (if there
578 are periods of least 7 symptom-free calendar days before and after the period with symptoms).

579 **Exposure variable**

580 See “Exposure variable” in section 5.2.

581 **Treatment effect measure**

582 We will measure treatment effect using a population-averaged incidence rate ratio (IRR) that compares
583 rates of teacher-events with symptoms in intervention and control schools. Section 5.1 describes how
584 estimation will be performed.

585
586 Treatment effect will be estimated following the intention-to-treat (ITT) principle: all teachers from all
587 randomized schools will be included and analyzed in the arms to which they were randomized.

588 **Strategy for handling missing data**

589 We will handle missing data using the approach described in section 5.1.

590 **Strategy for handling intercurrent events**

591 See Section 5.1.

592 **5.4 Secondary estimand — Teachers reporting respiratory infections odd ratio**

593 **Research question**

594 This secondary estimand addresses the question “Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA

595 filters in classrooms reduce number of teachers reporting respiratory infections?”.

596 **Population**

597 Primary school teachers in Norway.

598 **Outcome variable**

599 The outcome for this estimand is **teacher_infection**, a dichotomous variable that measures
600 whether each teacher meets the case definition for respiratory infection (see section 6.3) at any point
601 from randomization to the end of follow-up.

602 **Treatment effect measure**

603 We will measure treatment effect using a marginal odds ratio (OR). The treatment effect will be
604 estimated following the (ITT) principle: all teachers from all randomized schools will be included and
605 analyzed in the arms to which they were randomized.

606 **Strategy for handling missing data**

607 We will handle missing data using the approach described in section 5.1.

608 **Strategy for handling intercurrent events**

609 See Section 5.1.

610 **5.5 Secondary estimand — Teachers’ perceptions of air quality mean difference**

611 **Research question**

612 This secondary estimand addresses the question “Does installing and operating air purifiers with HEPA
613 filters improve teachers’ perceptions of air quality in classrooms?”.

614 **Population**

615 Primary school teachers in Norway.

616 **Outcome variable**

617 The outcome for this estimand is **teacher_mm040**, a score on the MM040 questionnaire, measured
618 at the level of teacher, at the end of the 3-month post-randomization period (note that teacher is
619 clustered within school). We will treat the score as a continuous variable.

620
621 We will use the MM040 questionnaire to ask teachers whether they have experienced drafts, high
622 room temperature, low room temperature, fluctuating room temperature, stuffy or “bad” air, dry air,
623 unpleasant odors, noise, or dust in the air during follow-up. The response options will be: "Yes, often
624 (every week)," "Yes, occasionally," or "No, never". The questionnaire will be presented in Norwegian.

625
626 We will also assess symptoms experienced by teachers during follow-up using the same response
627 options.

628 **Treatment effect measure**

629 We will measure treatment effect using a population-averaged mean difference (MD) comparing mean
630 scores in intervention and control schools. Section 10.2 describes how estimation will be performed.

631
632
633 Treatment effect will be estimated following the intention-to-treat (ITT) principle: all teachers from all
634 randomized schools will be included and analyzed in the arms to which they were randomized.

635 **Strategy for handling missing data**

636 If outcome data are missing for >5% of observations, then we will report Lee bounds for the mean

637 difference [8]. Lee bounds provide an interval estimate on a mean difference where the limits of the
638 interval correspond to point estimates that maximally favor and disfavor the intervention and hence
639 account for all possible missing data mechanisms.

640 **Strategy for handling intercurrent events**

641 See section 5.1.

642 **5.6 Secondary estimand — Adverse event rate ratio**

643 **Research question**

644 This secondary estimand addresses the question “What is the rate of adverse events in schools with
645 air purifiers with HEPA filters, and is this rate different in school with sham air purifiers?”

646 **Population**

647 Primary schools in Norway.

648 **Outcome variable**

649 The outcome for this estimand is **adverse_events**, the number of times that air purifiers were
650 reported to significantly disrupt lessons or cause accidents or injuries. The variable is therefore a count.
651 The variable is defined in section 3.5.

652 **Exposure variable**

653 See “Exposure variable” in section 5.1.

654 **Treatment effect measure**

655 We will measure treatment effect using a population-averaged incidence rate ratio (IRR) that compares
656 rates of adverse events in intervention and control schools. Section 10.1 describes how estimation will
657 be performed. However, see section 3.5, which describes how we will use the **adverse_events**
658 variable to monitor trial safety and the acceptability of air purifiers.

659
660 Treatment effect will be estimated following the intention-to-treat (ITT) principle: all schools will be
661 included and analyzed in the arms to which they were randomized.

662 **Strategy for handling missing data**

663 Data for this outcome cannot be missing because the variable is defined as the number of reported
664 adverse events. If no adverse events are reported, then the number of adverse events reported is zero.

665 **Strategy for handling intercurrent events**

666 See section 5.1.

667

668

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673 **6 Adherence**

674 Each participating school will designate a contact person (e.g., a school janitor) who will be responsible
675 for ensuring that the air purifiers are operated in accordance with the study protocol. This individual
676 will monitor and maintain the functionality of the devices according to a maintenance schedule and
677 will be instructed to promptly report any deviations or issues to the research team. The research team

678 may then take appropriate remedial actions, such as replacing a defective device, in a way that is
 679 similar to how such remedial actions could be taken if air purifiers were used outside of the trial context
 680 (e.g., during an epidemic or pandemic). By establishing this role, we aim to maintain protocol
 681 adherence and address potential disruptions.

682 7 Sample size and stopping boundaries

683 We designed this cluster-randomized group sequential trial using Stata's `gsdesign` command and
 684 the sample size formula published by Li et al., [9], which we identified from the scoping review of Zhan
 685 et al [10]. The trial is designed to detect an IRR of 0.85 at a two-sided overall alpha of 0.05 and overall
 686 power of at least 90% using the following assumptions, which were informed by data from our six-
 687 week pilot study in five schools: 3 months of follow-up; 20 schooldays per month; a mean of 23
 688 students per classroom; a mean of 1.36 classrooms per school (cluster size), with a standard deviation
 689 of 0.63; a 5.56% probability of a control student being absent on a given school day; an overdispersion
 690 factor of 2; an intraclass correlation coefficient of 0.3; a 20% probability of school (cluster) dropout; a
 691 1% probability of student dropout (e.g., transfer to another school); one interim analysis at an
 692 information fraction of 0.5; and error-spending O'Brien-Fleming-style boundaries for efficacy and
 693 nonbinding futility [11, 12]. Under these assumptions, we expect a total of 76 and 65 student absences
 694 in the control and intervention arms, respectively. The group sequential design, including the
 695 **cumulative** sample sizes and stopping boundaries, are shown in Table 3.
 696

Table 3. Group sequential design

Look	Information fraction	Stopping boundary z-values		Cumulative sample sizes	
		Efficacy (binding)	Futility (nonbinding)	Control schools	Intervention schools
1	0.5	±2.9626	±0.3447	16	16
2	1.0	±1.9686	±1.9686	31	31

697 We will recruit and randomize a total of 32 schools for the first look (interim analysis) and, if the trial
 698 continues to the second look, an additional 30 schools (for a maximum total of 62 schools if the trial
 699 continues after the interim analysis).
 700

701 To evaluate the trial's operating characteristics, we conducted a comprehensive simulation study that
 702 considered four treatment effect scenarios: IRR = 1.00 (null), 0.90 (small effect), 0.85 (target effect),
 703 and 0.70 (large effect). The simulation used 1000 trial realizations per scenario. Each simulated trial
 704 was analyzed with and without bias-correction (see section 10). We present empirical: type I error (for
 705 IRR = 1.00) or power; uncorrected and bias-corrected expected IRRs (on the log IRR scale); uncorrected
 706 and bias-corrected bias (on the log IRR scale); and coverage of uncorrected and corrected 95%
 707 confidence intervals on the estimated IRRs. For each quantity, we present marginal (i.e., averaged over
 708 the possible adaptations) and conditional (adaptation-specific). Results are presented as means and
 709 95% confidence intervals in Table 4. The shaded cells indicate where the trial operates outside the
 710 specified parameters (see the discussion below).
 711

712
 713
 714
 715
 716 Table 4. Trial operating characteristics

	IRR = 1.00	IRR = 0.90	IRR = 0.85	IRR = 0.70
Marginal				
N	1000	1000	1000	1000
Type I error / Power	.056 (.042 to .070)	.446 (.415 to .477)	.759 (.732 to .786)	.999 (.997 to 1.001)
Uncorrected estimate	.999 (.996 to 1.002)	.901 (.898 to .905)	.850 (.847 to .854)	.699 (.697 to .702)
Corrected estimate	.999 (.995 to 1.003)	.900 (.896 to .903)	.849 (.846 to .852)	.701 (.698 to .704)

Uncorrected bias	-.001 (-.004 to .002)	.001 (-.002 to .005)	.000 (-.003 to .004)	-.001 (-.005 to .003)
Corrected bias	-.001 (-.005 to .003)	-.000 (-.004 to .003)	-.001 (-.005 to .003)	.001 (-.003 to .005)
Uncorrected coverage	.944 (.930 to .958)	.954 (.941 to .967)	.961 (.949 to .973)	.991 (.985 to .997)
Corrected coverage	.959 (.947 to .971)	.951 (.938 to .964)	.961 (.949 to .973)	.985 (.977 to .993)
Continued to 2nd look				
N	988	915	772	135
Uncorrected estimate	.999 (.996 to 1.003)	.907 (.904 to .910)	.862 (.859 to .866)	.737 (.731 to .744)
Corrected estimate	.999 (.996 to 1.003)	.903 (.900 to .907)	.855 (.851 to .859)	.719 (.711 to .726)
Uncorrected bias	-.001 (-.004 to .003)	.008 (.004 to .011)	.015 (.011 to .018)	.052 (.043 to .061)
Corrected bias	-.001 (-.004 to .003)	.004 (-.000 to .007)	.006 (.002 to .010)	.026 (.016 to .037)
Uncorrected coverage	.946 (.932 to .960)	.953 (.939 to .967)	.952 (.937 to .967)	.948 (.911 to .986)
Corrected coverage	.959 (.946 to .971)	.946 (.932 to .961)	.952 (.937 to .967)	.956 (.921 to .990)
Stopped for benefit				
N	7	85	228	865
Uncorrected estimate	NE	.841 (.831 to .850)	.811 (.805 to .816)	.693 (.691 to .696)
Corrected estimate	NE	.861 (.850 to .873)	.828 (.822 to .835)	.698 (.695 to .701)
Uncorrected bias	NE	-.068 (-.079 to -.057)	-.047 (-.054 to -.041)	-.009 (-.013 to -.005)
Corrected bias	NE	-.044 (-.057 to -.031)	-.026 (-.033 to -.018)	-.002 (-.007 to .002)
Uncorrected coverage	NE	.965 (.925 to 1.000)	.991 (.979 to 1.000)	.998 (.994 to 1.000)
Corrected coverage	NE	1.000 (1.000 to 1.000)	.991 (.979 to 1.000)	.990 (.983 to .996)
Stopped for harm				
N	5	0	0	0
Uncorrected estimate	NE	NE	NE	NE
Corrected estimate	NE	NE	NE	NE
Uncorrected bias	NE	NE	NE	NE
Corrected bias	NE	NE	NE	NE
Uncorrected coverage	NE	NE	NE	NE
Corrected coverage	NE	NE	NE	NE

NE: Not estimable (results that would be based on fewer than 10 replications have been suppressed).

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The simulations show that the trial is likely to operate with the specified type I error, but with less power (76% versus 90%). [9] This is likely due to several differences between the simpler scenario addressed by Li et al. [9], and the one addressed in this trial, which includes adjustment for temporal variability in repeated measurements of the outcome, and use of maximum likelihood estimation with cluster-robust standard errors versus generalized estimating equations.

The marginal operating characteristics for uncorrected and bias-corrected estimates are similar. However, if the trial continues to the second look or is stopped for benefit, uncorrected estimates are likely to be substantially more biased towards an exaggerated treatment effect estimate than the bias-corrected estimates. For example, bias for uncorrected estimates may be 2× or 3× that of bias-corrected estimates. Empirical coverage of 95% confidence intervals is at least nominal for both methods.

Finally, at the target IRR of 0.85, the simulations suggest there is 77% chance the trial will continue to the second look, and a 23% chance that it will stop at the interim.

739 8 General Analysis Considerations

740 8.1 Timing of Analyses

741 First look (interim analysis)

742 Data will be collected for the first look (interim analysis) over a 3-month post-randomization period
743 during winter 2025/2026. Analysis will be performed for the primary estimand once data for all
744 estimands are finalized. If a decision is made to stop the trial for efficacy, the remaining analyses will
745 be performed. If a decision is made to continue the trial to the second look, we will not perform any
746 other analyses.

747 **Second look**

748 If the trial continues to the second look, data will be collected over a 3-month post-randomization
749 period during winter 2026/2027. Analysis will be performed for all estimands once all data are
750 finalized.

751 **8.2 Analysis Sets**

752 Section 3.2 defines two populations, students and teachers, so there will be one analysis set for each
753 of these populations. In addition, analysis sets will be defined to support the subgroup analyses (see
754 section 8.3). In practice there will be a single data set with one class per row, with one variable for
755 each outcome and covariate (section 8.3), as well as variables that identify treatment assignment,
756 school, and class.

757 **8.3 Covariates and Subgroups**

758 We will use the following variables to support analyses of subgroups (for factor variables) and
759 interactions (for continuous variables).

- 760
- 761 1. Geographical region (e.g., urban vs rural schools)
- 762 2. School size (e.g., small vs large schools)
- 763 3. Building age (e.g., older vs new buildings)
- 764 4. Ventilation system type (e.g., mixing vs displacement ventilation)
- 765 5. Co2
- 766 6. Median household income after tax.

767

768 The choice of these variables is based on the hypothesis that treatment effect may differ by
769 geographical region, school size, building age, ventilation system type, and household income,
770 potentially influencing the effectiveness of installing and operating air purifiers in different settings.
771 For example, schools in urban areas may have higher baseline air pollution levels than rural schools,
772 leaving more room for improvement with air purifiers. Similarly, larger schools with more students
773 may experience higher levels of airborne contaminants, potentially leading to a greater treatment
774 effect. Older school buildings may have poorer ventilation and higher pollution accumulation, which
775 could make air purifiers more impactful compared to newer buildings. Lastly, schools with mixing
776 ventilation may already have a better air quality, leaving less room for improvement compared to
777 displacement ventilated classrooms. Children from lower-income households may have higher
778 baseline respiratory vulnerability due to socioeconomic health disparities and greater cumulative
779 exposure to environmental stressors at home and in their neighborhoods, potentially making them
780 more responsive to school-based air quality improvements.

781

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784 **8.4 Multiple Centers**

785 We will not combine outcomes by classroom or school (i.e., we will not define “pseudo-clusters”). We
786 will not explore intervention-by-school interactions. Between-school differences in factors (including
787 but not limited to difference in adherence) will be accounted for by random effects with school (the
788 unit of randomization) as the cluster variable.

789 **8.5 Intercurrent Events**

790 We have determined that there are no intercurrent events that we need to plan to account for in the
 791 design or analysis (see section 5.1’s “Strategy for handling intercurrent events”).

792 **9 Summary of Study Data**

793 A CONSORT trial flow diagram will be presented. A table of baseline characteristics (e.g., number of
 794 classes, average classroom size, and average number of students per class) will be presented following
 795 CONSORT guidelines as in Table 5.
 796

Table 5. Baseline characteristics

			Sham Air Purifiers	Air Purifiers
Schools		N	XX	XX
	Urban	N (%)	XX (XX.X%)	XX (XX.X%)
	Rural	N (%)	XX (XX.X%)	XX (XX.X%)
	School age*	Mean (SD)	XX (XX.X%)	XX (XX.X%)
	Median household income	Mean (SD)	XX (XX.X%)	XX (XX.X%)
Classrooms		N	XX	XX
	Included per school	Mean (SD)	X.X (X.X)	X.X (X.X)
	Classroom area (m ²)	Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
	CO ₂ concentration (ppm)	Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
	Mixing ventilation	N (%)	XX (XX.X%)	XX (XX.X%)
	Displacement ventilation	N (%)	XX (XX.X%)	XX (XX.X%)
	Students		N	XX
Included per school		Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
Included per class		Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
Days of absence (3 months pre-randomization)		Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
Teachers		N	XX	XX
	Included per school	Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
	Days of absence (3 months pre-randomization)	Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)
	MM 040 score	Mean (SD)	XX.X (XX.X)	XX.X (XX.X)

*Years since construction or last major renovation.

797
 798 Effect estimates for the primary and secondary estimands will be reported as in Table 6, and results
 799 for count outcomes presented graphically as illustrated by the example Figure 2. The significance
 800 levels for the confidence intervals are presented in section 11. We will explore possible treatment
 801 effect modification for the primary estimand, and report results according to Table 7. We will perform
 802 subgroup analyses for categorical baseline covariates, and treatment × variable interactions for
 803 continuous baseline covariates.

804

Table 6. Results for the primary and secondary estimands.

	Sham Purifiers	Air Purifiers	Air Purifiers	Incidence Rate Ratio	p-value ⁴	Difference (XX.X% CI) ⁵	ICC ⁶	
Primary estimand (outcome measured on students)								
	Events	Exposure ¹	Events	Exposure ¹				
Absence	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX	XX.XX (XX.XX to XX.XX)	.XXX
Secondary estimands (outcomes measured on teachers)								
	Events	Exposure ²	Events	Exposure ²				
Absence	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX	XX.XX (XX.XX to XX.XX)	.XXX
Symptoms	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX	XX.XX (XX.XX to XX.XX)	.XXX
Adverse events	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX	XX.XX (XX.XX to XX.XX)	.XXX
	Mean (SD)		Mean (SD)		Mean Difference (XX.X% CI)	p-value		ICC
MM 040 score	XX.X (XX.X)		XX.X (XX.X)		XX.XX (XX.XX to XX.XX)	.XXX	XX.XX (XX.XX to XX.XX)	.XXX

Notes: 1. Exposure is measured in units of student-days. 2. Exposure is measured in units of teacher-days. 3. Bias-corrected point estimate and confidence interval. 4. p-value from the group sequential test (not bias-corrected). 5. Difference is measured in units of events per student or teacher week. 6. Between-period intraclass correlation coefficient.

805

806

807

808

Table 7. Subgroups and interaction analysis results.

	Sham Air Purifiers	Air Purifiers	Incidence Rate Ratio	p-value ³	Difference (XX.X% CI) ⁴	ICC ⁵
	Events	Exposure ¹	Events	Exposure ¹	(XX.X% CI) ²	
Geographical Area						
Urban	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX
Rural	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX
School age ⁶	NA	NA	NA	NA	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX
Ventilation						
Mixing	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX
Displacement	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX
log CO ₂ ⁷	NA	NA	NA	NA	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX
Median household income	NA	NA	NA	NA	X.XX (X.XX to X.XX)	.XXX

Notes: 1. Exposure is measured in units of student-days. 2. Bias-corrected point estimate and confidence interval. 3. For categorical covariates, p-values test null hypotheses of no differences in treatment effect; for treatment × covariate interactions, p-values test null hypotheses of no interaction. 4. Difference is measured in units of events per student or teacher week. 5. Between-period intraclass correlation coefficient. 6. Treatment × school age interaction. 7. Treatment × log CO₂ concentration interaction.

809

810

Figure 2 Results for count outcomes

811

812 9.1 Derived Variables

813 We will measure baseline CO₂ concentration in units of parts per million (ppm). In the pilot study, CO₂
814 concentration was observed to range between about 400 to 1600 ppm with positive skewness. We will
815 therefore log-transform baseline CO₂ concentration to derive a variable with magnitudes, range, and
816 skewness that are more amenable to analysis, both for the covariate-constrained randomization and
817 the adjusted analyses. We do not anticipate CO₂ values as low as zero, so log CO₂ should be well-
818 defined.

819
820 We will use log mean rate of student absences in each school in the covariate-constrained
821 randomization (see section 3.3). The linear predictor used to estimate IRRs is also defined on the log
822 rate metric, so it is also sensible to define the **school_logabsrate** variable on the log metric for
823 the adjusted analyses. However, there may be some schools for which no students are absent in the
824 pre-randomization phase, which could result in an undefined log rate. We therefore define the variable
825 **school_logabsrate** as

$$826 \text{school_logabsrate} = \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{E_T} \sum_i y_{(-i)}\right)$$

828 where $y_{(-i)}$ is **student_absence**, the same variable as used to define the outcome, measured i
829 weeks pre-randomization, E_T is the total exposure during the pre-randomization phase of the trial,
830 and the sum is implicitly taken over all classrooms in a given school and over the pre-randomization
831 phase. In other words, **school_logabsrate** is the log of one plus the pre-randomization mean
832 rate for the school. The “1 +” term ensures that if the sum evaluates to zero, then
833 **school_logabsrate** is well-defined and evaluates to zero. Finally, while **school_logabsrate**
834 could be computed by implementing the summation above, in practice it could be computed in
835 whichever way is most convenient given the data.

836
837 We do not plan to derive or transform any other variables, except as explained elsewhere in this
838 document.
839

840 9.2 Protocol Deviations

841 Any deviations from the original protocol or this SAP will be reported and justified in the trial report
842 under the subheading “Protocol deviations”.

843 10 Estimation and Analyses

Important note: The Stata syntax used in this section is intended to be illustrative of the methods
we intend to use and is not intended to be implemented exactly as shown.

844 10.1 Incidence rate ratio estimation

845 *Structure of the data*

846 We anticipate that the count outcome data will be measured each week. The following therefore
847 assumes we will have panel (longitudinal) data, where **classroom** is the panel variable and **week** is
848 the time variable. If during the pre-randomization trial period we discover that schools can only report
849 outcomes at the end of the three-month period of the trial (or with some other frequency), so that the
850 data have a different structure than anticipated, we will publish a revised version of this SAP.

851
852

853 **Estimator**

854 We seek to estimate a marginal (population-averaged) incidence rate ratio and anticipate that the
855 counts will be overdispersed. We will therefore use Stata’s **nbreg** to fit a negative binomial model.
856 We will use marginal standardization to obtain marginal (population-averaged) incidence rate ratio
857 estimates, marginalizing over the empirical distribution of covariates and follow-up time.

858 **Accounting for temporal variation**

859 It is possible that absences, infections, and adverse events may exhibit temporal variation due to
860 changing community infection pressure over time. To account for this, we will include indicator
861 variables for trial week (fixed effects that adjust for temporal variation in background risk).
862

863 Additionally, the timing of vinterferie varies across schools in the study. To account for this, we will
864 include an indicator variable for whether a given school-week corresponds to vinterferie (fixed effect),
865 ensuring that comparisons between trial arms are not confounded by differences in holiday timing.

866 **Accounting for the cluster-randomized design**

867 We will account for the cluster-randomized design by computing cluster-robust standard errors (and
868 hence confidence intervals and *p*-values) with **school** as the cluster variable. We will report a model-
869 based intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) using a mixed-effect model with random effects at the
870 level of **school**, assuming a constant correlation in repeated measures on the same individual over
871 time [13].

872 **Accounting for the constrained randomization**

873 Treatment will be assigned using covariate-constrained randomization, where the constraining
874 variables are log baseline CO₂ concentration (**school_logco2**), log student absence rate
875 (**school_logabsrate**), school ventilation type (**ventilation**), and median household income
876 (**income**), which we assume are prognostic. The European Medicines Agency and US Food and Drug
877 Administration (FDA) guidance respectively suggest and allow adjusting for prognostic covariates on
878 the basis that doing so will often provide more precise estimates of treatment effect [14, 15]. However,
879 we lack empirical evidence that the constraining variables are prognostic. It is therefore possible that
880 these covariates are not prognostic — or their effect is smaller than this trial will be able to estimate
881 — and that adjusting for them might introduce bias or reduce efficiency, yielding a less precise
882 estimate of treatment effect.

883
884 To address this problem, we prespecify a model selection strategy in which we will select among the
885 $2^4 = 16$ possible adjustments (excluding interactions) using the consistent version of Akaike’s
886 information criterion (AIC) [16]. The models are:

- 887
- 888 1. Not adjusted for either covariate used in the constrained randomization.
- 889 2. Adjusted only for **school_logco2**.
- 890 3. Adjusted only for **school_logabsrate**.
- 891 4. Adjusted only for **ventilation**.
- 892 5. Adjusted for **school_logco2** and **school_logabsrate**.
- 893 6. Adjusted for **school_logco2** and **ventilation**.
- 894 ...
- 895 16. Adjusted for **school_logco2**, **school_logabsrate**, **ventilation**, and **income**.

896
897
898

899 **Estimation**

900 We will arrange the data with one row per week. At the first look, we will use syntax like the following
901 to obtain the z-statistic for the group sequential test (note that no bias correction is applied at this
902 point and the example syntax omits any covariates that would be included on the basis of the approach
903 described above):

```
904  
905 nbreg y i.treat i.week, ///  
906 exposure(exposure) irr dispersion(constant) vce(cluster school)  
907
```

908 where **y** is the outcome variable (e.g., number of student absences), **treat** is a treatment indicator
909 variable, **week** is a factor variable that models week, **exposure** is the exposure variable, and
910 **school** is the cluster variable.

911
912 Once the trial is stopped (either at the first or second look), a bias-corrected estimate of the
913 population-average treatment effect will be obtained as follows. We will use conditional maximum
914 likelihood to estimate the model parameters, conditional on the realized adaptation, using the same
915 model specification. The approach is described in more detail below. We will then use marginal
916 standardization to obtain a population-averaged IRR using syntax like the following:

```
917  
918 margins , at(treat = (0 1)) predict(ir) post  
919 nlcom _b[1._at] / _b[2._at]  
920
```

921 We will use a similar approach to report an estimate of the difference in the number of events expected
922 each week between the control and intervention conditions.

923 **Accounting for the group sequential design**

924 The group sequential design allows for a possible second look, which would include data collected
925 during a subsequent winter season. Because baseline rates may differ between winter seasons, we will
926 adjust for this possible temporal variation in the same way as for the first look—by including indicator
927 variables for study week (i.e., week fixed effects) in the model to account for within-season fluctuations
928 in background risk. Weeks from the second look (winter 2026/2027) will be assigned a distinct set of
929 week codes from those used for the first look (winter 2025/2026), ensuring that baseline rates and
930 temporal trends are modelled separately for each season.

931
932 While the trial is designed to protect the overall type I and II error probabilities, point estimates for
933 group sequential trials can be biased (see table 4). The standard error for an estimate obtained at an
934 early look will be relatively large due to the relatively small sample size available at that look, so the
935 point estimate is expected to be relatively far from the true value; if the observed effect is sufficiently
936 large that the group sequential test statistic crosses a stopping boundary, the uncorrected point
937 estimate can be expected to be excessively large in the direction of the stopping boundary (i.e., the
938 point estimate will be biased).

939
940 The decision to stop the trial early will be made by comparing the z-value for the group sequential test
941 for the primary estimand to the prespecified boundaries for efficacy. We will report bias-corrected
942 effect estimates, and *p*-values from the group sequential test (i.e., obtained from the uncorrected
943 analysis). We will use the *p*-value to draw our conclusions about efficacy and will use the bias-corrected
944 estimate, as suggested by Grayling and Wason (2023) and in line with the FDA guidance on adaptive
945 trials [17], to provide the best estimate of the magnitude and direction of treatment effect. It is
946 important to note that bias-corrected point estimates serve a different inferential purpose than the
947 group sequential test. Consequently, the confidence interval around a bias-corrected estimate may
948 include the null value despite the trial having stopped early for demonstrated efficacy.

949

950 The operating characteristics presented in table 4 are based on the method below (see section 2.2.5
951 of Grayling and Wason 2023). The bias-corrected effect estimate is obtained by solving the following
952 maximization problem

$$953 \hat{\theta}(k, z) = \arg \max_{\theta} f_c(k, z | \theta)$$

954
955 where θ is log incidence rate ratio, z is the value of the z-statistic corresponding to the uncorrected
956 estimate of log incidence rate ratio, and k indexes look. Rather than use analytical approximations to
957 the conditional likelihood, simulations suggest that simulation-based estimates of the conditional
958 component perform better.
959

960 **10.2 Mean Difference Estimation**

961 ***Structure of the data***

962 We will estimate a mean difference in the continuous variable `teacher_mm040` (teacher score on
963 the MM040 questionnaire), which is measured once for each teacher, with repeated measures within
964 school.

965 ***Estimator***

966 We seek to estimate a population-averaged mean difference that accounts for the clustering of teacher
967 within school. We will therefore use Stata's `cnsreg` to fit a normal model (`cnsreg` is use instead of
968 `regress`, because it is necessary to use constraints to maximize the conditional likelihood to apply
969 the bias correction described above).

970 ***Accounting for temporal variation***

971 Since the `teacher_mm040` variable is measured once, rather than repeatedly, it is not necessary to
972 account for temporal variation in this analysis.

973 ***Accounting for the cluster-randomized design***

974 We will account for the cluster-randomized design using cluster-robust standard errors with school as
975 the cluster variable.

976 ***Accounting for the constrained randomization***

977 We will account for the constrained randomization using the same strategy as for incidence rate ratios
978 (i.e., by selecting between unadjusted and adjusted models using AIC).

979 ***Estimation***

980 Estimation will be performed in a similar manner as for the IRR. Estimation will be based on syntax like
981 the following (the example omits any covariates that would be included on the basis of the approach
982 described above and does not demonstrate the bias correction):

```
983  
984 cnsreg teacher_mm040 i.treat i.week, vce(cluster school)
```

985
986 It is not necessary to use marginal standardization because the mean difference is a collapsible effect
987 measure.

988 ***Accounting for the group sequential design***

989 The group sequential design allows for a possible second look. A second look would include data
990 collected during a different winter season, which may result in a difference in the mean score in the
991 control arm. We will account for this in the same way as for the IRR estimator (i.e., using AIC to

992 selection from the possible models). We will apply the same bias-correction procedure as used for the
993 IRR estimator (conditional maximum likelihood).

994 **10.3 Odds ratio estimation**

995 ***Structure of the data***

996 We will estimate an odds ratio for the dichotomous variable `teacher_infection`, which is
997 measured once for each teacher, with repeated measures within school.

998 ***Estimator***

999 We seek to estimate a population-averaged odds ratio that accounts for the clustering of teacher
1000 within school. We will therefore use Stata's `logit` and marginal standardization as described
1001 previously.

1002 ***Accounting for temporal variation***

1003 Since the `teacher_infection` variable is measured once, rather than repeatedly, it is not
1004 necessary to account for temporal variation in this analysis.

1005 ***Accounting for the cluster-randomized design***

1006 We will account for the cluster-randomized design using cluster-robust standard errors where
1007 `school` is the cluster variable.

1008 ***Accounting for the constrained randomization***

1009 We will account for the constrained randomization by selecting among models using AIC as described
1010 previously.

1011 ***Estimation***

1012 Estimation will be performed in a similar manner as for the IRR. Estimation will be based on syntax like
1013 the following (the example omits any covariates that would be included on the basis of the approach
1014 described above and does not demonstrate the bias correction):

```
1015  
1016 logit teacher_mm040 i.treat , vce(cluster school)  
1017
```

1018 We will then use marginal standardization to obtain a population-averaged OR using syntax like that
1019 presented for the IRR estimator.

1020 ***Accounting for the group sequential design***

1021 The group sequential design allows for a possible second look. A second look would include data
1022 collected during a different winter season, which may result in a difference in the mean score in the
1023 control arm. We will account for this in the same way as for the IRR estimator (i.e., using AIC to select
1024 from the possible models).

1025 **10.4 Subgroup and interaction analyses**

1026 We investigate the potential effect modifiers proposed in section 9. We will estimate treatment effects
1027 in subgroups by restricting the estimation sample by subgroup and using the same analysis methods
1028 as described in section 10, modifying the model specification as necessary. We will report p -values for
1029 treatment \times subgroup and treatment \times covariate interactions by including the interaction terms in the
1030 models.

1031 **11 Reporting Conventions**

1032 In general, percentages in the table of baseline characteristics will be rounded to whole numbers, and
1033 summaries of continuous variables will be presented to one decimal place.

1034
1035 We will report treatment effect estimates as point estimates and two-sided 95% confidence intervals
1036 constructed using appropriate critical values based on the realized adaptation, to maintain strong
1037 control of the 95% coverage probability (type I error). We will report two-sided confidence intervals
1038 and *p-values*, as appropriate, throughout. Point estimates and confidence intervals will be reported to
1039 2 decimal places, and *p-values* will be reported to three decimal places or as $p < 0.001$, or according to
1040 a target journal's house style.

1041 **12 Quality Assurance of Statistical Programming**

1042 We will develop statistical analysis and reporting code for the primary estimand and first look using
1043 fictitious (simulated) data, assuming no more than 5% of observations (rows) are incomplete with
1044 respect to the variables that will be used to estimate the primary estimand. Before analyzing the first
1045 look data, we will test that the code can produce the primary estimand row of the main table of results,
1046 excluding the numbers of events and exposures to allow the decision to stop or continue the trial to
1047 be made while blinded (see section 3.4). If there is substantial missing data we may choose to develop
1048 the analysis and reporting code for the primary estimand against the trial data (with the statistician
1049 blinded). In this case, we will report and justify any analysis choices that may be driven by the nature
1050 of the trial data.

1051
1052 Once the trial has been stopped (i.e., after the first or second looks), we will develop all remaining
1053 statistical analysis and reporting code. Again, we will use fictitious data but may choose to use the trial
1054 data if complete are available for less than 95% of observations (rows). In particular, the code to
1055 produce the table of baseline characteristics will only be developed after the trial has been stopped to
1056 minimize the risk that a decision is taken to stop or continue the trial based on any perceived imbalance
1057 in baseline characteristics. Assuming we develop the analysis code against fictitious data, we will test
1058 that the code can produce all results, tables, and figures as they will appear in the final manuscript
1059 prior to analyzing the finalized trial data.

1060
1061 Analysis code and data will be versioned using an appropriate system to be chosen by the analyst and
1062 may be published alongside the trial results.

1063 **13 Summary of Changes to the Protocol and/or SAP**

1064 This SAP was updated during follow-up on 13 March 2026 (before any data were available for analysis)
1065 to revise the bias-correction method and handling of vinterferie.

1066
1067 Rather than apply an analytic conditional maximum likelihood correction to estimates obtained from
1068 estimators based on generalized estimating equations, the method was revised to apply conditional
1069 maximum likelihood correction to maximum likelihood models, estimating the conditional likelihood
1070 using simulation. This update was based on extensive simulation-based validation experiments that
1071 demonstrated that the revised approach has better operating characteristics.

1072
1073 The previous version of this SAP incorrectly assumed that all schools would observe vinterferie in the
1074 same week. This version corrects this, and plans analyses that adjust for the differential observance.

1075 **14 Acknowledgements**

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1077 Michigan Institute for Clinical and Health Research (MICHHR; grant UL1TR002240), which was based in
1078 turn on version CCTU/TPLV2 of the template produced by Cambridge University Hospitals Clinical Trials
1079 Unit.

1080 **15 References**

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